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Data Review

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Abstract

The Opposition Movements and Groups (OMG) dataset is a global dataset on large-scale political mobilization campaigns that challenge or preserve the core features of a political regime or a polity's territorial integrity. The dataset spans the period from 1789 to 2019 and covers 151 countries. The unit of analysis in OMG is the campaign phase. A campaign is defined as a series of temporally contiguous, organized collective actions pursuing a political objective related to regime change, institutional reform, leadership removal or preservation, or territorial autonomy or secession.

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Review of the Opposition Movements and Groups dataset

by Stas Gorelik

The Opposition Movements and Groups (OMG) dataset is a global dataset on large-scale political mobilization campaigns that challenge or preserve the core features of a political regime or a polity's territorial integrity. Developed by a research team mostly associated with the Peace Research Institute Oslo, OMG is designed to capture sustained campaigns of collective action rather than discrete protest events.

The dataset spans the period from 1789 to 2019 and covers 151 countries, making it one of the longest-running and most extensive datasets on organized political contention currently available.

The unit of analysis in OMG is the campaign phase. A campaign is defined as a series of temporally contiguous, organized collective actions pursuing a political objective related to regime change, institutional reform, leadership removal or preservation, or territorial autonomy or secession. Campaigns may consist of multiple phases, reflecting periods of activation, inactivity, or shifts in demands or political context. Variables are coded separately for each phase, allowing researchers to trace changes within campaigns over time.

OMG differs from most protest-event datasets in several important respects. First, it is campaign-centered rather than event-centered; instead of recording individual demonstrations, it aggregates sustained mobilization efforts. Second, the dataset focuses on substantive political demands, coding both primary and secondary objectives across a wide range of categories, including: regime removal, institutional reform, civil rights, elections, executive constraints, autonomy, and secession. Third, OMG systematically records organizational involvement, social group participation, leadership structure, ideological orientation, and the use of violent and non-violent tactics.

For post-Soviet states, OMG includes campaigns beginning in the late Soviet period and continuing through the post-1991 era, with particularly dense coverage from the late 1980s onward. This includes mobilization campaigns in Russia, Ukraine, the Baltic states, the South Caucasus, and Central Asia, covering independence movements, regime-challenging campaigns, and post-independence institutional conflicts.

Data access: <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.7910/DVN/G4FCZO>.

Related publications:

Dahl, M., S. Dahlum, H. Fjelde, H. Gjerløw, C. H. Knutsen, C. Strøm-Sedgwick & T. Wig (2025). "Mass Mobilization in the Modern Era: Introducing the Opposition Movements and

Groups (OMG) Dataset, 1789–2019.” Comparative Political Studies. DOI:
10.1177/00104140251369330.